

Newsletter 2 / 2023

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Spread the word

ESiWACE3 taking over: Third funding phase has been launched

The third phase of the project, ESIWACE3, has officially started!

On 1 and 2 February 2023, the Kick-Off Meeting of ESIWACE3 was held on the premises of the [Barcelona Supercomputing Center \(BSC\)](#) in Barcelona.

This new funding phase of the project focuses on supporting the weather and climate modelling community to reach a higher readiness level regarding exascale supercomputing, and on fostering knowledge transfer between the different Earth system modelling centres and teams across Europe. Co-funded by the [European High Performance](#)

[Computing Joint Undertaking](#) (EuroHPC JU) under the powers delegated by the European Commission (EC), ESIWACE3 is led by the BSC and will run for 4 years (January 2023–December 2026) as [one of the 10 new Centres of Excellence in High Performance Computing](#). More information about ESIWACE3 is available [here](#).

Last issue of the ESIWACE2 newsletter: We are saying goodbye!

Dear readers of the ESIWACE newsletter,

With the transition to ESIWACE3, both the project coordination and the communication teams are changing. This is the last newsletter issue prepared by the ESIWACE2 team, and we would like to express our sincere gratitude to both you as our readership and to the numerous ESIWACE colleagues who have contributed to the project and newsletter content within the last years.

In case you have been receiving this newsletter via the ESIWACE news list hosted at DKRZ, together with the ESIWACE3 team (led by BSC), we will get in touch with you regarding the renewal of your newsletter subscription for the third funding phase.

We wish you all the best and hope that you will continue to follow ESIWACE3 and its activities in the future!

Best wishes,

Joachim Biercamp, Julia Duras & Dela Spickermann for the ESIWACE2 project office

IS-ENES3 Webinar: Cylc, a workflow engine with support for cycling systems

When: Thursday March 16th, 10:00-11:00 am CET

IS-ENES3 is offering a free webinar introducing the general purpose workflow engine [Cylc](#). Cylc, which has also been supported within ESIWACE, is used for production weather, climate, and environmental forecasting on HPC systems, but is not specialised to those domains and therefore applicable beyond.

In this 45 + 15 minute webinar, Oliver Sanders from the Met Office will explain what Cylc is, will introduce its main features and cover recent developments.

In order to receive the connection link, **please register before March 14th**: <https://forms.gle/CJBspLc4wGTPqsCCA>

Events that ESIWACE will participate in or has participated in

- [EuroHPC Summit](#), Gothenburg (SE), 20-23 March, 2023
- [EGU General Assembly 2023](#), Vienna (AT) + online, 23–28 April, 2023
- [ISC High Performance 2023](#), Hamburg (DE), 21-25 May, 2023

News & updates

ESiWACE2 Final General Assembly & ESiWACE3 Kick-Off Meeting in Barcelona

From January 30 until February 2, 2023, [Barcelona Supercomputing Center \(BSC\)](#) hosted two consecutive meetings of ESiWACE: The Final General Assembly of ESiWACE phase 2 and the Kick-Off Meeting of ESiWACE3, [one of the 10 new Centres of Excellence in High Performance Computing](#) launched on January 1, 2023 by the European High Performance Computing Joint Undertaking (EuroHPC JU) within the scope of the [Horizon Europe EU funding programme](#).

With BSC taking over the role of project coordinator for the third funding phase from DKRZ, having the two project meetings back-to-back at the BSC premises was a natural choice. This format allowed the ESiWACE2 consortium members to reflect and report on progress and achievements made during the second project funding phase, to inform new ESiWACE3 partners accordingly, to work on open tasks and to prepare the transition to ESiWACE3 and beyond.

In three lively plenary discussions, the consortium members took a peek into the crystal ball: Mario Acosta (BSC) and Peter Dueben (ECMWF) engaged the attendees in a discussion on “The next 5 years for the four WP1 production mode models”: IFS, EC-Earth, ICON, IPSL, NEMO. Widening the perspective, Peter Dueben and the attendees then discussed their vision of “What will we do different in weather and climate modelling in 2035?”. In a third plenary session Ben van Werkhoven (NLeSC) and Sophie Valcke (CERFACS) addressed the future of the ESiWACE services delivered within the second funding phase; plans for services in ESiWACE3, gaps and alternative ways to sustain the service activities.

On Wednesday, February 1 the ESiWACE3 Kick-Off Meeting was opened by Francisco Doblas-Reyes, head of the Department of Earth Sciences at BSC, and Mario Acosta, head of the High Performance Computing team at the Earth Science Department, both project co-coordinators, setting the stage and context. Their welcome and introduction was followed by invited presentations on the ENES-RI by Fanny Adloff (DKRZ), the thematically neighbouring CoE ChEESE

(Centre of Excellence for Exascale in Solid Earth) by Josep de la Puente (BSC), the obligations of Horizon Europe-funded projects by Linda Gesenhues (EuroHPC JU), as well as introductory presentations on all seven ESIWACE3 work packages and an invited presentation on Destination Earth delivered remotely by Nils Wedi (ECMWF). The meeting was complemented by diverse breakout groups including debriefing and a dedicated session on management and coordination.

For more information on the achievements of ESIWACE in its first two funding phases, please have a look at our [public deliverables and milestones on Zenodo](#).

Revisiting the Blue Marble: ICON simulating the coupled climate system at 1 km

To celebrate the 50th anniversary of the famous “Blue Marble” photo, taken by the Apollo 17 crew at 10:39 UTC on 7 December 1972, a team from the Max Planck Institute of Meteorology, DKRZ and NVIDIA simulated the actual weather of that date and the following two days using the ICON weather and climate model on DKRZ’s new

supercomputer Levante. The coupled ICON simulation was run at a horizontal resolution of 1 km and a vertical resolution with 90 vertical levels in the atmosphere (about 3 hundred million grid points per level) and 128 vertical levels in the ocean (about 2 hundred million surface grid points). The atmosphere uses a time-step of 8s and the ocean of 45s. The simulation was run on 900 nodes of Levante, about one-third of the total supercomputer, and achieved a throughput of about 3 simulated days per day. The ICON simulation was initialised from a spun-up ocean state corresponding to two days before the famous photograph was taken, and simulated the following 3 days in 1972. It is remarkable that the simulation captured the conditions of the Blue Marble so well, as there were very limited observations going into the reanalysis at the time, especially for the southern hemisphere that the famous photo depicts.

This work has been supported by the European and German national projects NextGEMS, WarmWorld and ESIWACE. For further reading, see the [detailed article](#) published on the website of the Max Planck Institute of Meteorology. The visualisation video "Apollo 17 Blue Marble simulated with the ICON climate model at 1 km resolution" is available [here](#) on DKRZ's YouTube channel.

Recently published ESIWACE2 Deliverables

ESIWACE2 on the home stretch: With the second funding phase coming to an end by 31 March 2023, we have ramped up our efforts and have released a number of project deliverables the previous months:

D2.1: Report summarising the adaptation of the proposed DSLs and the evaluation of the benchmarks and models proposed in this project

Deliverable D2.1 discusses extensions and improvements on the two domain-specific languages (DSLs) in use within the ESIWACE2 project, PSyclone and dusk/dawn, in order for them to support the Weather and Climate models: NEMO, LFRic, and ICON. The content is complemented by a comparison of PSyclone and dusk/dawn using a NEMO benchmark, and the topic of interoperability between those two DSLs is addressed. [Read D2.1 here](#)

D2.7: Second white paper on community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications

This deliverable summarises state-of-the-art advancements related to HPC infrastructures, heterogeneous architectures and machine learning related to climate and weather applications as tracked by Work Package 2. In addition to tracking and compiling the efforts in literature, the WP2 colleagues organised a second virtual workshop on Emerging Technologies for Weather and Climate Modelling in October 2022. The workshop content is documented in this deliverable through the presentation abstracts, and the majority of workshop presentations is available in the [workshop playlist](#) on the [ESIWACE YouTube channel](#). [Read D2.7 here](#)

D2.9: Final Report on Porting Earth System Models to Containers

The containerisation of atmosphere and ocean models with complex dependencies, external configurations, and performance requirements helps to provide a consistent environment to ensure security, portability and performance on multiple platforms. In this deliverable we document the multi-year effort to containerise key models from the climate / numerical weather prediction community, led by ETH Zurich and kicked off through the container hackathon for modellers in 2019. D2.9 provides an overview of containerisation efforts on the models EC-Earth, LFRic, COSMO and ICON, as well as references to the public online documentation developed by the respective teams. [Read D2.9 here](#)

D3.2: Report on services in portability and refactoring

With computing infrastructure rapidly evolving, existing software such as complex weather and climate models needs to be adapted in order to make efficient use of state-of-the-art hardware architectures. To support weather and climate modelling groups in code refactoring and the portability of their model codes to different platforms, Work Package 3 established short collaborative projects within the scope of ESIWACE2 “Service 1: Model portability and refactoring”. Deliverable D3.2 summarises the results of ten such Service 1 projects delivered and illustrates how each of the codes, e.g. RegCM, OBLIMAP2 and MicroHH, could advance towards exascale in the future. [Read D3.2 here](#)

D3.3: Report on services offered on IO, coupling and workflow

Within the scope of “Service 2: Coupling, IO and workflows” of ESIWACE2 Work Package 3, the weather and climate modelling community had had the chance to apply for and receive dedicated support for the optimal usage of three community tools: the OASIS3-MCT coupler, the XIOS IO server, and the Cylc workflow engine. Deliverable D3.3 presents an overview of the respective services provided. [Read D3.3 here](#)

D3.5: To make Europe's Earth system models fit for the exascale

Modern exascale supercomputers increasingly rely on GPUs as the major source of compute power. However, existing weather and climate modelling codes were designed to run on traditional CPU-based supercomputers and require a significant adaptation effort in order to make efficient use of these new systems. To assist weather and climate modelling groups in this endeavour, ESIWACE2 offered three services, providing guidance, engineering, and advice via collaborative projects. D3.5 reports in detail on the Service 1 projects RegCM and MicroHH, and gives a summary of all three Services provided via Work Package 3. The deliverable concludes with valuable lessons learned, bottlenecks on the path to exascale and associated challenges to be addressed in the near future. [Read D3.5 here](#)

D4.3: Software documentation and roadmap

As managing data from modern high-resolution weather and climate simulations is becoming problematic due to the sheer data deluge, novel solutions are needed. In this deliverable we present a summary of two classes of middleware software developed and / or improved in ESIWACE2 that help to overcome this challenge both during and after simulations: 1) Tools for in-flight analysis of ensembles of simulations, ideally supporting cross-ensemble calculations, and 2) Middleware for managing writing data to disk and managing the migration of data through storage tiers. [Read D4.3 here](#)

D5.3: Report on the final implementation of key selected post-processing, analytics and visualisation applications and main outcomes

Deliverable D5.3 presents the recent developments in Work Package 5 since the publication of [D5.2](#) on core routines for post-processing, analytics and visualisation (PAV) applications plus their interplay with the ESDM documented in [D4.1](#). The recently published D5.3 details on improvements made regarding the selected PAV applications Ophidia, CDO and ParaView, and also introduces the newly developed YAVIZ interface for online (in-transit) diagnostics and visualisation with models that use the YAC coupler. [Read D5.3 here](#)

Snapshots

BSC

BSC organised the ESIWACE3 Kick-Off Meeting and also co-organised and hosted the Final General Assembly of ESIWACE2 at the BSC premises in Barcelona (ES).

CERFACS

CERFACS finalised deliverable D3.3 reporting on the services offered on I/O, coupling and workflow during ESIWACE2 and participated in the final general assembly in Barcelona.

CMCC

CMCC contributed in WP5 to deliverable D5.3 “Report on the final implementation of key selected post-processing, analytics and visualisation applications and main outcomes” describing the key developments in WP5 related to the ESDM-PAV and Ophidia and the results from the performance evaluation of the Ophidia extensions for in-flight analytics. Moreover, in WP2, CMCC led the writing of deliverable D2.7 “Second white paper on community guidelines on the use, value and applicability of emerging technologies in climate and weather applications” collecting the results from a state-of-the-art analysis on emerging technologies together with the key outcomes from the 2nd workshop on emerging technologies, held in October 2022.

DKRZ

MPI-M now uses the python bindings for YAC developed by DKRZ in WP5 for the output in a test run for the nextGEMS cycle 3 simulations. These efforts receive continued support from DKRZ. YAC3 with an overhauled interface that streamlines its use in in-transit analysis is getting close to its release. The integration of the ESIWACE2 improvements to the ParaView CDI reader into the official code repository and CI system has been completed.

Experts of DKRZ and ATOS used the opportunity of the project meeting in January to work intensively together on streamlining several aspects of HPCW, in particular setting up and consolidating the framework on the DKRZ system.

Furthermore, for the second phase of the [DYAMOND initiative](#) “[DYAMOND Winter](#)”, MPI-M and DKRZ are developing a workflow for an automated file deletion on disk and a user-friendly data access with easy file retrieval from the DKRZ tape archive. This will ensure a convenient data access beyond the end of the ESIWACE2 support for DYAMOND.

In addition to keeping track of and finalising and submitting project deliverables and milestones, we at the project office (WP7) have co-organised the ESIWACE2 Final General Assembly back-to-back with the ESIWACE3 Kick-Off Meeting at BSC in Barcelona. Our work in progress includes the ESIWACE2 final report and the preparation of the final review meeting with the European Commission, as well as the transfer of dissemination and communication channels and activities to our colleagues at BSC for ESIWACE3.

ETH Zürich / CSCS

With the Deliverable D2.9 “*Final Report on Porting Earth System Models to Containers*”, ETH Zürich / CSCS has completed its contribution to WP2 in ESIWACE2. D2.9 reports on the experiences of inserting Earth system models – LFRic, COSMO, ICON and EC-Earth – into containers. The effort coincides with concrete efforts to utilise containers in the production workflow for LFRic, COSMO and ICON.

From the inception of ESIWACE2, performance loss of running models within containers in production was identified as a central risk. It turns out that the container overhead is quite small (<5%) if the application is run with a HPC-aware container run-time environment such as Singularity (<https://sylabs.io>) or SARUS (<https://products.cscs.ch/sarus>). The following figure illustrates the strong scalability of a 20km global resolution

Quasi-Biennial Oscillation ICON benchmark proposed by Dr. Marco Giorgetta (MPI-M), run both within and without (“bare-metal”) a container on 64-256 Nvidia P100 GPU nodes of CSCS Piz Daint. The timings for the bare-metal and container versions virtually coincide when the jobs are run one after the other within the same allocation to minimise the effect of changing system and I/O subsystem load. In fact, the time overhead of the containerised version is considerably less than the time variability of the benchmark with changing system load. We view this and other results as a clear indication that containers can be an effective tool in HPC development and deployment, particularly since they can assure a much longer lifetime of the software stack underlying a given simulation.

ETH Zürich / CSCS is now completing a port of HPCW benchmarks to the new CSCS Alps architecture as part of WP3. Sadly we will not participate in ESIWACE3 due to the evolving political relationship between Switzerland and the EU. We sincerely thank all our ESIWACE2 partners for the valuable and stimulating collaborations over the last four years, and wish you all the best in your new endeavours.

Recent ESIWACE2-related Publications

Harris, L., McRae, A. T. T., Chantry, M., Dueben, P. D., & Palmer, T. N.: A generative deep learning approach to stochastic downscaling of precipitation forecasts. *Journal of Advances in Modeling Earth Systems*, 14, e2022MS003120. <https://doi.org/10.1029/2022MS003120>, 2022.

Stijn Heldens, Alessio Sclocco, Henk Dreuning, Ben van Werkhoven, Pieter Hijma, Jason Maassen, Rob V. van Nieuwpoort: *litstudy: A Python package for literature reviews. SoftwareX, Volume 20, 101207, ISSN 2352-7110.*
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.softx.2022.101207>, 2022.

Veerman, M. A., van Stratum, B. J. H., & van Heerwaarden, C. C.: *A case study of cumulus convection over land in cloud-resolving simulations with a coupled ray tracer. Geophysical Research Letters, 49, e2022GL100808.*
<https://doi.org/10.1029/2022GL100808>, 2022.

Hohenegger, C., Korn, P., Linardakis, L., Redler, R., Schnur, R., Adamidis, P., Bao, J., Bastin, S., Behraves, M., Bergemann, M., Biercamp, J., Bockelmann, H., Brokopf, R., Brüggemann, N., Casaroli, L., Chegini, F., Datsis, G., Esch, M., George, G., Giorgetta, M., Gutjahr, O., Haak, H., Hanke, M., Ilyina, T., Jahns, T., Jungclaus, J., Kern, M., Klocke, D., Kluft, L., Kölling, T., Kornbluh, L., Kosukhin, S., Kroll, C., Lee, J., Mauritsen, T., Mehlmann, C., Mieslinger, T., Naumann, A. K., Paccini, L., Peinado, A., Praturi, D. S., Putrasahan, D., Rast, S., Riddick, T., Roeber, N., Schmidt, H., Schulzweida, U., Schütte, F., Segura, H., Shevchenko, R., Singh, V., Specht, M., Stephan, C. C., von Storch, J.-S., Vogel, R., Wengel, C., Winkler, M., Ziemann, F., Marotzke, J., and Stevens, B.: *ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales, Geosci. Model Dev., 16, 779–811,*
<https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023>, 2023.

News from the neighbors

nextGEMS Hackathon goes into the 3rd Cycle!

From **Monday, 29 May to Friday, 2 June 2023** our partner [project nextGEMS](#) organises its **Cycle 3 Hackathon in Madrid**. The participants will sit together in small groups working on a topic related to one of the four nextGEMS research themes, as well as to marine ecosystem and fishery. These topics will be explored by working with the storm-resolving data of the nextGEMS Cycle 3 simulations run by the IFS and ICON models, identify bugs and improvements, and ultimately prepare for the nextGEMS production runs. **Guests from partnering projects:** WarmWorld, EERIE and Destination Earth are welcome and **up to 15 stipends** for participation in the Cycle 3 Hackathon to support young scientists (at Master and PhD student level) from outside the project.

Registration: <https://events.mpimet.mpg.de/event/56/> Open until **Monday, Apr 3, 2023!**

Stipend application: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/call-for-applications-join-our-cycle-3-hackathon-with-a-stipend/>
Open until **Monday, Apr 3, 2023!**

Open positions

Computer Scientist for dynamical core development ESIWACE3 position at ECMWF

ECMWF has a new position to help introduce and optimise the Domain Specific Language GT4Py into their new dynamical core FVM as part of the ESIWACE Centre of Excellence. Please help spread the word.

<https://jobs.ecmwf.int/displayjob.aspx?jobid=132>

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